

DOMAINS OF ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE THAT BEST PREDICTS THE WORK STRESS AMONG GOVERNMENT EMPLOYEES IN DAVAO CITY

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ABSTRACT

The study aims to determine which domains of organizational culture that best predicts the work stress among government employees in Davao City. The level of organizational culture among government employees exhibited a high level with the mean rating of 3.93 while the level of work stress showed a moderate level with a mean rating of 2.52. However, there is negative relationship between the organizational culture and work stress, and none of the six parameters of organizational culture directly influences the work stress. Descriptive correlation method of research was used in the study and was conducted among different government agencies with 175 respondents. Data analysis showed that there is significant relationship between organizational culture and work stress but none of the six parameters of organizational culture directly influences the work stress of the government employees.

Keywords:

Organizational culture, work stress, government employees, descriptive-correlational research, Davao City, Philippines

INTRODUCTION

Work stress can affect the productivity performance of an employee, it can also be detrimental to one's health and well-being (Wainwright and Calnan, 2002). According to the American Psychological Association's annual Stress in America survey conducted in 2012, 65 percent of Americans cited work as a top source of stress. This being said states work stress could be one of the major problems the economic state is facing, not only hurting institutions but most especially individuals.

With the pressure of deadlines and various projects at hand in work, the organizational culture of establishment plays a role in accumulation or mitigation of stress. When the beliefs, ideologies, principles and values of individuals in an organization meet, unity, loyalty, healthy competition, direction and identity can be achieved connoting that organizational culture can affect the success of the organization (Lowe, 2018).

However, a negative effect as employees cope up with work stress would seem to generate toxic culture. Withdrawal behavior, wherein employees show and perform in disinterest because of intent to quit, and service sabotage, wherein an employee intentionally jeopardize customer service, can be developed (Costa, 2016). These behaviors further work stress and creates a negative cycle to formation of new organizational culture, the type that would not inspire the success of the organization.

Despite the urgency of a solution to this problem, the researchers have found out that there are not enough studies focusing on work stress and its relationship to organizational culture. This calls the need to conduct this study.

FRAMEWORK

The culture within an organization plays a critical role in the organization's everyday operations. Lundy & Cowling (1996), defines organizational culture as "the way we do things around here," as cited in the International Journal of Business Management in 2008. Generally speaking, organizational culture is defined as the deeply rooted morals and principles that are common among all people in an organization.

Dominant Characteristics. There are practices within organization's that tend to keep a culture alive and measure the cultural fit between the organization and its employees. Dominant characteristics refer to organizational beliefs and practices that influence the workers norm, customs and philosophical stances. Employees who are well acculturated also find their work more meaningful: they are part of, and contributing to, something larger than themselves (Gilsdorf, 2007).

Organizational Leadership. Leaders are considered to be coordinators and organizers. They are also thought to be hard drivers, producers, competitors, innovators and risk takers (Cameron, 2010). By setting the mission of an organization and empowering employees to achieve that mission, leadership build grounds of the organization's culture and plays an essential role in changing it when it needs to be changed (Greesonbach, 2015).

Management of Employees. Security of employment, conformity, predictability and stability in relationships are important as leadership and culture are linked to organizational performance. The claim that organizational culture is linked to management style is founded on the perceived role that culture can play in generating competitive advantage. As the organization develops and time passes, the created culture of the organization exerts an influence on the leader and shapes the actions and style of the leader (Ogbonna & Harris, 2000).

Organization Glue. According to Freiling & Fitchner (2010), organizational culture promotes the process of learning and competence building and functions as glue between people and the organization they belong to. It's the invisible glue that holds an organization together and ultimately makes the difference between whether an organization is able to succeed or not.

Strategic Emphases. It is the most important factor in an organization that causes effectiveness and significance to the workers outcome. In psychology literature, organization's culture, conceptualization and approaches are the method to produce relevant outcomes. The key to successful and effective organization is in the right strategies formulated and applied in running it (Roberts & Pallock, 2014).

Criteria of Success. According to Role (2012), it is the working environment that moves an organization. The leaders' attitude and management in handling the workers can affect positively or negatively. Physical job demand (work overload), salary (high work, low reward), time pressure

(unable to meet the deadline due to work load) and job security and stability may affect the performance of employees that contribute to high success rate of organization (Awadh I. et al., 2015). Work stress on the other hand is a topic of major concern among organizations. Work stress is thought to affect individual's psychological and physical health, as well as organization's effectiveness, in an adverse manner. Workers who are stressed are also more likely to be unhealthy, poorly motivated, less productive and less safe at work. Their organizations are less likely to be successful in the competitive market (Leka, et. al., 2003).

Demands of the job. A factor that contributes to work stress is the amount of demands of the job, especially when a worker experiences decrease in autonomy. According to Jafar Akbari, Rouhollah Akbari and Behzad Mahaki (2012), the demands of the job has a significant relationship to job control because when a worker is put in this situation, he is not able to perform a defending behavior that is experienced in active jobs and may only be perceived as a "challenge."

Lack of control. It was found out that even when there is increase in demands of the job, as long as the worker is given his freedom to set his own goals and the process of the job, the stress from it may still be considered beneficial as compared to increase in demands of the job but no flexibility. With this work stress, the impact becomes detrimental causing 15.4% increase risk of dying. When a worker is not given flexibility at work, he may resolve to resources to deal with the stress such as smoking and the like (Gonzales-Mule, 2016).

Work-life balance. As technology has made almost everyone accessible, it has also caused its cons to workers causing them to work beyond 9-5. This does not only inflict health but also relationships and overall happiness (Lee, 2014).

Relationships at work. Given that work stress may be inevitable, a study conducted by Le Van Thanh (2016) in the context of Vietnamese culture concluded that work stress can be tolerable when the relationship at work is healthy enough to support workers in responding to it.

Change. Uncertainty for a future stability may cause change in work field, restructuring and introducing new management techniques may also cause change, but change is a need to progress. Employee growth and development is a necessary tool to lift organization's success. Acquiring new set of knowledge and skills may also boost the confidence of workers that may affect their commitment in team's goal and enhancement (Divakar, J., 2015).

Conflicting roles. When workers are affected by work stress, they may become easily angered, irritable, less committed to work, anxious and enjoy their work less. This especially, when there are unclear roles, conflicting roles in the same job, and responsibility with the people (Leka, S. 2003).

Working Environment. According to Kundaragi, P. & Kadakol, A. (1984), environmental stressors are noise, traffic, weather, pollution and crime. Many studies confirm that physical health can unfavorably affect the working environment with poor hygiene and other degrading facilities that will lead to stress.

The effects of work stress is not limited to the social and personal damage of an employee, and does not limit to common sicknesses but can lead to alarming conditions such as hypertension, cardiovascular diseases and decreased mental health that its fatality may lead to death (White, 2015). Commonly overseen, work stress should be addressed in the pursuit of building healthy organizational culture.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study was conducted to determine the level of organizational culture, level of work stress, significant relationship between organizational culture and work stress, and the domains of organizational culture that best predicts the work stress among government employees.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive correlation method of research was used in the study. The goal is the acquisition of factual, accurate and systematic data that can be used in averages, frequencies and similar statistical

calculations. The study was conducted among different government agencies in Davao City, Philippines to 175 respondents. Mean, standard deviation, correlation and linear regression were the statistical tools used for the data analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the analysis and interpretation of data gathered.

As presented in Table 1, the level of organizational culture among government employees, they exhibited a high level with the mean rating of 3.93. This means that organizational culture is a powerful force that influences the behavior, attitude and disposition of the members of the organization, which also coincides with Ahadi (2011) that organizational culture is a powerful influence on the holistic empowerment of an employee because it describes the link between contextual factors and employees' work behaviors. All the six factors discloses high level with a mean ratings of 4.02 for organization glue, 3.99 for strategic emphases, 3.91 for organizational leadership, 3.90 for management of employees, 3.89 for criteria of success and 3.87 for dominant characteristics respectively. Moreover, the Standard Deviation shows homogeneity of the responses among respondents.

Table 1. Level of Organizational Culture among Government Employees

Organizational Culture	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Dominant Characteristics	0.57	3.87	High
2. Organizational Leadership	0.68	3.91	High
3. Management of Employees	0.65	3.90	High
4. Organization Glue	0.66	4.02	High
5. Strategic Emphases	0.67	3.99	High
6. Criteria of Success	0.70	3.89	High
Overall	0.56	3.93	High

Presented in Table 2 is the level of work stress among government employees and this showed a moderate level of stress with a mean rating of 2.52. This means that the level of work stress of the government employees is just reasonable; it's not severe or relatively extreme. The findings agree with Wlodarski, et. al. (2006) that there are diverse factors that contribute to a stress level of a person; its family life, health, career, emotional problems, economical disposition and many more. The seven factors disclose two different level of work stress; the moderate and low level. The factors with moderate level of work stress are demands of the job with a mean rating of 2.89, lack of control with a mean rating of 2.54, and change with a mean rating of 2.78 respectively. On the other hand, the factors with low level of work stress are the following; 2.49 for the work-life balance, 2.18 for relationships at work, 2.34 for conflicting roles, and 2.41 for working environments respectively. Moreover, the standard deviation shows homogeneity of the responses among respondents.

Table 2. Level of Work Stress among Government Employees

Work Stress	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Demands of the Job	0.79	2.89	Moderate
2. Lack of Control	0.77	2.54	Moderate
3. Work-life Balance	0.98	2.49	Low
4. Relationships at Work	0.88	2.18	Low
5. Change	0.83	2.78	Moderate
6. Conflicting Roles	1.05	2.34	Low
7. Working Environment	0.93	2.41	Low
Overall	0.68	2.52	Moderate

Presented in Table 3 is the relationship between organizational culture and work stress of government employees which showed a negative relationship. As revealed in the r-value of $-.321$ with a p-value of $.000$ which is less than $.05$ level of significance, this implies that the work stress of the government employees is dependent on the organizational culture. This implies further that, the higher level of organizational culture, the lower stress level among government employees. Hallkos, George (2008) affirms this on his study on “*The influence of stress and satisfaction on productivity,*” wherein he stated that work stress is dependently related to organizational culture. When organizational culture functions as a motivator, work stress results in creativity and satisfaction and consequently removes boredom and mundanity. Stress leads to aggression and low job satisfaction when organizational culture functions as a negative factor.

In addition, all the indicators of the organizational culture contributed an inverse relationship to the work stress of the government employees. Thus, there is significant relationship between organizational culture and work stress.

Table 3. Relationship between Organizational Culture and Work Stress of Government Employees

		Overall	decision
Dominant Characteristic	Pearson Correlation	$-.237^{**}$	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	$.002$	
Organizational Leadership	Pearson Correlation	$-.282^{**}$	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	$.000$	
Management of Employees	Pearson Correlation	$-.274^{**}$	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	$.000$	
Organization Glue	Pearson Correlation	$-.264^{**}$	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	$.000$	
Strategic Emphases	Pearson Correlation	$-.278^{**}$	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	$.000$	
Criteria of Success	Pearson Correlation	$-.296^{**}$	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	$.000$	
Overall	Pearson Correlation	$-.321^{**}$	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	$.000$	

Presented in Table 4 are the domains of organizational culture predicting the work stress of government employees which shows that none of the six parameters of organizational culture directly influences the work stress of the government employees as shown on their p-values which are all above the $.05$ level of significance. On the other hand, as revealed in the r-square of $.105$, f-value of 3.283 and p-value of $.004$ which is less than $.05$ level of significance, this implies that if the six indicators of organizational culture are gathered together it will be enough to have a significant value on the work stress of the government employees. Thus, the higher the level of organizational culture, the lower is the stress among government employees.

Table 4. Domains of Organizational Culture Predicting the Work Stress of Government Employees

Organizational Culture	Work Stress			
	Beta	t-value	p-value	Decision on Ho
1. Dominant Characteristics	$-.052$	$-.427$	$.670$	Accept Ho
2. Organizational Leadership	$-.096$	$-.810$	$.419$	Accept Ho
3. Management of Employees	$-.035$	$-.267$	$.790$	Accept Ho
4. Organization Glue	$-.040$	$-.335$	$.738$	Accept Ho

5. Strategic Emphases	-.051	-.382	.703	Accept Ho
6. Criteria of Success	-.117	-.901	.369	Accept Ho
R-square: .105 F-value=3.283 P-value=.004				
Regression Equation: $Y=4.056-.056X_1-.096X_2-.035X_3-.040X_4-.051X_5-.117X_6$				

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the researcher concluded that the level of organizational culture among government employees exhibited a high level with the mean rating of 3.93 while the level of work stress showed a moderate level with a mean rating of 2.52. However, there is negative relationship between the organizational culture and work stress. All the indicators of the organizational culture contributed an inverse relationship to the work stress but none of the six parameters of organizational culture directly influences the work stress of the government employees. Moreover, the higher level of organizational culture, the lower stress level among government employees.

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